

National Press Associates

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

This is awarded to

राज लक्ष्मी

For Publication of Paper Titled

सूचना प्रौद्योगिकी और ग्रामीण महिला श्रमिक: डिजिटल साक्षरता, रोजगार पहुँच और सामाजिक परिवर्तन का अध्ययन

For National Research Journal Titled

“National Research Journal of Sales and Marketing Management”

Peer Reviewed Refereed Research Journal

Volume-12, Issue No: 2, Year: 2025 (July-December)

ISSN: 2349-512X

Impact Factor: 6.95

Publisher

Website:

www.npajournals.org